

Weaving a Sustainable Future: Reviving Assam's Golden Muga Silk Legacy by an Innovative Microfinance Project

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Abstract: Background: Sualkuchi, Assam, is renowned for its exquisite Muga silk weaving tradition. This tradition of Sualkuchi itself has a system of indigenous knowledge generation and has been sustained as the self-independent economy of the community since ancient times. The Muga silk weaving and associated indigenous culture is a valuable cultural heritage that contributes to the region's identity and tourism. However, weavers or artisans often face financial hardship and social demotivation for the tradition. Moreover, the low profitability despite hard labor associated with the traditional Muga silk weaving is a significant concern. Additionally, transitioning weavers to service-oriented company jobs raises questions about working conditions, job security, and the potential loss of artisanal skills. Thus, the tension between preserving tradition and ensuring economic viability is a serious dilemma faced by government as well as social organizations trying to maintain a balance between cultural preservation and modernity. Therefore, it is essential to find ways to increase the income of silk weavers without compromising the craft, and associated cultural as well as philosophical and spiritual heritage. **Methods:** This observational ethnography study explores the potential of a community-based participatory action research (CBPAR) informed microfinance model to revitalize and preserve this Muga silk tradition of Sualkuchi. In this study, we have interviewed and organized focused group discussion with the silk weavers (n=10) KaviKrishna Living Muga Silk Museum. **Results:** KaviKrishna, an organization dedicated to supporting weavers since 1920, has implemented the Sustainable Livelihood Initiative for Weavers (SLIW) to provide comprehensive support, including financial assistance, market access, healthcare and education. By combining microfinance with cultural revitalization efforts such as reviving the Vedic Silk Route and the Indigenous Kamarupa Information Network (IKIN), SLIW aims to empower weavers, enhance their livelihoods, and contribute to the sustainable economic development of rural India. Preliminary findings suggest that this integrated approach can significantly improve the socioeconomic conditions of Muga silk weavers while preserving a valuable cultural heritage. **Conclusion:** SLIW may provide an innovative model for reviving this tradition and its knowledge generation for the upliftment of Sualkuchi's Muga silk heritage. Through this ethnography study we have formulated the following hypothesis: The CBPAR based KaviKrishna-microfinance model can revitalizing the IKIN, and in the process the social capital of the Muga silk weavers, and their cultural heritage.

Introduction: Muga silk, also known as "Golden Silk," is what truly makes the entire history of Silk road quite fascinating. Unlike mulberry or eri silk, Muga silk boasts a naturally occurring golden hue, shimmering with an unparalleled luster. This unique color comes from the silkworms that feed on the leaves of the Som and Soalu trees, indigenous to Assam. The entire process of Muga silk production, from silkworm rearing to weaving, is a testament to generations-old knowledge and meticulous craftsmanship (1).

Sualkuchi, nestled in the Kamrup district of Assam, India, is renowned for its vibrant Muga silk weaving tradition. The village has been synonymous with the exquisite art of Muga silk weaving since centuries (2). This tradition, steeped in history and cultural significance, stretches back centuries, intricately woven into the very fabric of Assamese life.

Muga silk transcends its breathtaking beauty to hold deep cultural and religious significance for Buddhists and Hindus alike. Its naturally golden hue, unlike any other silk, has earned it the title of "Golden Silk." Legends even claim that Buddha himself attained Nirvana clad in Muga silk, further solidifying its sacred status. Woven from the cocoons of semi-domesticated moths that feed on specific Assamese trees, Muga silk boasts an unmatched luster and a unique stiffness that drapes elegantly (1-3). For centuries, Buddhists and Hindus have sought Muga silk for religious offerings and spiritual ceremonies, believing its golden threads to be imbued with auspiciousness (4). This reverence for Muga silk extends beyond religious practices. In Assam, the shimmering Mekhela Chador crafted from Muga silk is an essential part of a woman's wardrobe, worn during festivals and passed down through generations as a treasured heirloom. Thus, Muga silk serves as a powerful symbol, not only of exquisite craftsmanship but also of the rich tapestry of Buddhist, Hindu, and indigenous Kamrupian traditions that continue to thrive in Assamese culture.

Sualkuchi: Where Golden Threads Muga Silk Weave a Legacy

Since the era of the Indus Valley civilization, where the thread of Muga silk was identified in a 3000 BC cultural complex (5), the Muga Silk history is a mystery of antiquity (6). Our decades of historical and ethnographic research indicate the existence of a Vedic age silk road that stretched from Central Asia to South East Asia via North and North East India (7). Sualkuchi was probably part of the putative Vedic Silk Road, as its rich history as a Muga silk weaving center extends to the Mauryan Empire (300 BC). Kautilya's Arthashastra, a product of the Empire mentions 'Sauvarnakudyaka', believed to be Muga silk from the ancient kingdom of Kamrupa, suggesting Sualkuchi's potential role in the Vedic Silk Road. References to Muga silk can also be found in the Kishkindha Kanda of the Ramayana. The epic describes a journey eastward, passing through Magadha, Anga, Pundra, and finally, the "Kosha-Karanam-Bhumi," the land of cocoon rearers (8). This further solidifies the historical significance of silk cultivation in the region. Moreover, the ancient temples of Sualkuchi-Hajo cultural complex, dating back to 600-800 CE, such as Hayagriva Madhava and Siddheswar Devalaya, have a longstanding tradition of using Muga cloth as sacred attire for religious ceremonies. A copper plate inscription from the 9th century, attributed to the Kamrupa Pala dynasty king, Dharma Pala, highlights the importance of Muga silk. The ruler actively promoted silk cultivation within his kingdom, bringing skilled weavers from Tantipara, a village near Barpeta, to establish a dedicated weaving community in Sualkuchi (2,7-9). This migration of skilled artisans marked the genesis of Sualkuchi's renowned Muga silk weaving

tradition. The Pala kings, including Dharma Pal, were not only patrons of the arts but also astute connoisseurs. They recognized the exquisite beauty and exceptional durability of Muga silk, setting it apart from other textiles. This royal appreciation for Muga silk led to its active patronage. Weavers, revered for their meticulous craftsmanship, were frequently invited to the royal courts. Their task: to create exquisite garments for royalty and dignitaries, adorning them in shimmering Muga silks that reflected both their status and the artistry of the craft. Royal patronage not only elevated the social status of Muga silk but also played a crucial role in its transmission through generations. Knowledge of Muga silk weaving techniques, passed down from father to son, mother to daughter, ensured the continuity of this precious craft. This royal connection also contributed to the development of the Sualkuchi and Hajo cultural complex.

The rise of Sualkuchi as a weaving hub was significantly influenced by the religious fervor surrounding the Kamakhya Temple in Guwahati. The temple's prominence attracted numerous devotees, creating a robust market for Muga silk, renowned for its sacred and aesthetic qualities. Simultaneously, the nearby Hayagriva Madhava temple further solidified the region's association with Muga silk, incorporating it into religious rituals. The symbiotic relationship between spirituality and commerce further solidified Sualkuchi's prominence. Under the patronage of the Koch and Ahom dynasties, Muga silk weaving flourished. The Ahom rulers, recognizing the cultural and economic significance of this craft, actively supported the weavers of Sualkuchi (1,2,9).

The Weavers of Sualkuchi: Custodians of a Golden Legacy, Facing Uncertain Times

Sualkuchi's beating heart lies in its community of skilled weavers. Their nimble hands, guided by knowledge passed down through generations, transform raw Muga silk into breathtaking tapestries. The rhythmic clacking of looms fills the air, a symphony that speaks of dedication and artistry. These weavers, often families who have carried the tradition for centuries, are the custodians of this unique cultural heritage.

Despite their dedication, the future of Sualkuchi's weavers is not without challenges. The 19th and early 20th centuries saw a devastating decline due to the influx of cheap, machine-made textiles as a result of British Raj's textile policies. Gandhi landed in Sualkuchi in 1946 to support the cause of our silk weavers. While post-independence India's nationalist governments offered some support, the industry subsequently faced new challenges (9).

Weavers often struggle to make ends meet, with the process of Muga silk production being labor-intensive and time-consuming. Competition from cheaper alternatives, both domestic and international, further squeezes their profit margins (9). The decline of Muga silk weaving is exemplified by Tantipara, KaviKrishna's origin, which boasted over 50 looms in the early 20th century but witnessed a complete loss of this tradition by the century's end.

The risk of losing these skilled artisans and their age-old knowledge is a very real threat. If the economic viability of Muga silk weaving is not ensured, this precious cultural heritage could fade away. The future of Muga silk weaving rests on a delicate balance. It requires continued support for the weavers, ensuring they are fairly compensated for their skill and artistry. It also necessitates fostering a renewed appreciation for Muga silk's unique qualities and cultural significance. Only

through such collective efforts can we ensure that the rhythmic clacking of looms in Sualkuchi continues to resonate for generations to come.

This is precisely why it is important to develop innovative microfinancing ways to empower the Muga silk weavers.

SLIW: A Holistic Approach on Microfinance is Born through KaviKrishna Living Muga Museum

The main goal of KaviKrishna Living Muga Museum is to revive the Muga Tradition cancer patient's rehabilitation and deprived weavers of Sualkuchi with an unique microfinance model managed by a CBPAR approach. This CBPAR approach has been initiated by KaviKrishna since 1994 for biomedical and clinical research (10-12). This unique CBPAR-based microfinance under the Sustainable Livelihood Initiative for Weavers (SLIW) initiative provides support to set up the Muga looms with capital money. After setting up the looms they can sell the Muga product to the KaviKrishna at a current market price with the deduction of the price of raw materials provided by KaviKrishna. In this way, Kavi Krishna provides all the profit to the weavers for a period of one year. The successful weavers then become part of a muga silk weaver network and produce plus sell their weaving products either to KaviKrishna or the market. Kavikrishna continue to offer social capital support to these weavers in terms of health, as well as education for their children as a part of the CBPAR initiative. The SLIW emerged from KaviKrishna's commitment to continuous improvement and a deep understanding of the weavers' needs. SLIW moved beyond traditional microfinance, and broke the mold of traditional microfinance. Instead of loans with interest, we provide weavers with the resources they need to thrive. This includes:

- **Financial Assistance:** SLIW offers direct funds to weavers to maintain their looms and ensure uninterrupted production.
- **Market Access:** We bridge the gap between weavers and potential customers by connecting them with temple-goers seeking high-quality silk offerings. This ensures fair market value for the weavers' products.
- **Healthcare Integration:** Recognizing the vital link between health and economic well-being, SLIW provides free consultations and medical care to participating weavers.
- **Research Integration:** Recognize the vital importance of investigating the health and biomedical use of muga silk yarn e.g. application in stem cell and space suit research.

So, far KaviKrishna has invested approximately Rs 1.5 crores in the SLIW project since 2010 (Jinti needs to get this audit done). In this ethnography study, we have explored the SLIW methods, and the potential of this approach as a novel model of Mirofinance.

Methodology: We have used a traditional method of Jiva Upakara Tantra (JUT) based qualitative research, the Satavata-tarka (10, 13). In this JUT based method, both inductive (prabartaka or Pratasthya) and deductive (anumana) inference (anumana) are combined in a dialectic manner (dbandika Upai) for an investigation (Anusandhan or Gobeshona). The Satavata-tarka is an iterative process (Punarabrittumulaka prakriya) where the dialogue takes places between a healer (one who enquires to solve a problem e.g. a researcher) and a given community (Samaj). The iterative process serves as a mechanism of learning as well as the emergence of wisdom, a process

known as Panchapadika (Figure 9, reference 7). This Satavata-tarka based research is similar to a modern combination of CBPAR, and ethnography (participant-observation), known as the community-based participant-observation. In the JUT-based CBPAR, emphasis is given to the re-activation of dormant social network of learning/knowledge system by engaging a few community members. Community workers, health experts, and other experts engage the community to define their perceptions of problems as well as aspirations. This initial process involves first generating a desire/goal (Iccha-Prataskhya or Inductive inference stage of Satavata Tarka) based on subjective-experiences (Anubhava or Perception) of a problem that is harming the community (Samaj). The next steps are engaging in dialogues (interviews including vignettes interviews, focused group discussion, suppositional reasoning and participant-observation) to obtain a core inference (Anuman-Yukti, which is a mixture of inductive and deductive inference as per Nyaya sashtra). This is equivalent to the coding ,and analytic memos of qualitative research methods. In the Dharana stage, a process of analysis is done (tathya bislesana) to compare the findings (the Anuman-yukti) with the previous findings, or prevalent social norms/wisdom. This is a process of manthan or synthesis. During this stage, community meetings, events, and cultural exhibitions may be conducted to further refine the Anuman-yukti process. Eventually, the tathya-bislesana, or data analysis process led to the emergence of Dharana (equivalent to the emergence of major theme in the thematic analysis and grounded theory methods). The Dharana is then described in “shabda” or reflection written in words (equivalent to analytical memos). The result of the entire process of satavata-tarka (the path of investigation or Anviksiki, <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Anviksiki>) is written down as a form of writing (descriptive writings, stories, poems or sloka) in the final stage, the Prajna-Agan (Supplementary methods in the reference 10). The solution provided in the Prajna-Agan is now then fed into the five stages of Pancha-Padika, thus fulfilling the Kriya (Krishna) part of the Satvata-Tarka. In this way, an iterative process emerges, which is equivalent to the modern notion of CBPAR, where the community is actively engaged in the research process, and the subsequent actions to solve a social or public health issue. The Dharana process is similar to the Photovoice method of CBPAR, where participants are asked to project their ideas (dharana) related to a particular social issue (16).

We have utilized the above methodology to explore the impact of the Sustainable Livelihood Initiative for Weavers (SLIW) microfinance project on the Muga silk weaving community in Sualkuchi, Assam. The Anuman-yukti data was gathered through in-depth interviews with 10 weavers, two focus group discussions with a total of 10 participants, and participant observations in several weaving workshops. The study was approved by the ethical committee of KaviKrishna Laboratory. Participants were included in the study following the proper consent. Several weavers taking medical services at KTC were also included as a part of the Medical Humanities program, and as per the ethical notion of the ,”Desa-kala-patra” (17). We also conducted several focused group discussions (FGD). The FGD session employed Satvata Tarka methods as previously explained (Nigudah paper). The interviews and FGD mediated data were analyzed to explore themes. For the theme generations, interviews and FGD generated stories as well as published books, and News Papers stories were transcribed. From these materials, recurring themes, concept and stories were categorized. Memo-writing, as well as themaptic analysis was practiced, and the results were utilized for the subsequent ethnographic interviews. In this manner, through triangulation process we obtained a coherent story about the development of the KaviKrishna microfinance process.

Results: Here, we describe the results first as the life story of the KaviKrishna's birth in 1920, and its evolution as the KaviKrishna Living Muga Silk Museum set up in 2018.

A Legacy of Supporting Weavers: The Evolution of KaviKrishna' microfinance tradition

The tradition of microfinance has been prevalent among the weaving communities of Sualkuchi since the 16th century, the establishment ear of Hatisatra (1650 AD). Many families have been freed from poverty through microfinance. In 1920, Krishna Samaj was born out of a microfinance project. Krishna Samaj used to lend money to people for Muga business purposes. The borrowed amount had to be repaid with interest during the Magh Bihu festival every year. For example, Uttam Medhi's father had taken a loan of Rs 68.75 (one thousand one hundred and fifty annas), when the price of a muga set was twenty-five annas (twenty-five paise). Heramba Choudhury (Duryodhan Choudhury's father) had taken a loan of Rs 131.25 (one thousand three hundred and thirty annas). Kamala Bura's father from Tantipara had taken a loan of around 500 annas. (These facts were narrated by Ranadeep Medhi's father, Prakash Medhi). However, Uttam Medhi's father could not repay the loan. Boliram Das (Krishna Das's father) had taken a loan of Rs 2,000 annas (two thousand annas) from Krishna Samaj for business purposes in Sivasagar. But he lost everything when his business vessel sank in the Brahmaputra River. Although after the independence movement in 1947, this society Krishna Samaj disintegrated but some members of Krishna Samaj consolidated to form the National Cooperative Weaving Society Limited in 1965. From 1965 to 1985, the old and new members of Krishna Samaj were involved in the cooperative movement. In 1972, the Indian government merged the microfinance and cooperative movements into a new economic development policy called 'Garibi Hatao' (Eradicate Poverty). On the other hand, Duryodhan Mahajan and his two sons, Khagen and Sada Choudhury, along with Tarun Choudhury, personally connected with nearly two hundred weavers through microfinance and established a large business of Gamosas (traditional scarves) and chadors (traditional garments). During the 1960-1990 period, this business flourished, and many shops were established in Sualkuchi and Jorhat. The success of microfinance was evident in the growth of these businesses. However, between 1990-2000, many weavers who had taken loans failed to repay them, and due to socio-cultural changes and a decline in the weaving industry, the personal microfinance system eventually collapsed. Uttam Medhi, another founding member of Krishna Samaj, like Duryodhan Choudhury, also successfully ran the weaving business through microfinance. Between 1980 and 1995, this business had a significant impact in Sualkuchi. In 2010, KaviKrishna was evolved as a successor of Krishna Samaj with a new vision in the field of weaving tradition of Sualkuchi by launching Cancer Patient Rehabilitation Program and the Sustainable Livelihood Initiative for Weavers (SLIW) in KaviKrishna Living Muga Museum and provide both commercial and academic aspect to the weaving tradition.

KaviKrishna's commitment to the weaving community of Sualkuchi stretches back to its very beginnings. Established in 1920, KaviKrishna initially functioned as a microfinance organization, providing weavers with loans to support their craft. Throughout the 1920s to 1950s, KaviKrishna employed a traditional microfinance model, offering loans with interest. While this approach aimed to empower weavers, it did not address the long-term challenges of debt burden and limited access to healthcare. In the following decades, KaviKrishna explored a cooperative society model of microfinance. This model aimed to create a more collaborative and self-sustaining system for weavers. However, this approach ultimately faced limitations and did

not fully address the weavers' needs. Facing the shortcomings of the cooperative model, many weavers found themselves relying on loans from other microfinance sources, often leading them back to a cycle of debt. Recognizing this, KaviKrishna embarked on a new path in the 1994.

Expanding the Circle of Support

SLIW's commitment extends beyond direct financial aid to weavers. Recognizing the interconnectedness of families, we offer additional support through:

- **Indirect Financial Assistance:** In some cases, we may help family members, particularly students, find employment opportunities within SLIW itself. This provides additional income for the weaver's household.
- **Educational Empowerment:** In some cases, we may provide students of weavers to embark on their academic journey to empower the community. To take forward this mission, we have started with the KaviKrishna Center of Indian Knowledge Systems now equipped with Master and PhD courses on Indian Knowledge Systems.
- **Comprehensive Cancer Care:** SLIW understands that cancer can be a devastating financial burden. We offer free healthcare services to weavers diagnosed with cancer, alleviating financial strain and allowing them to focus on recovery.
- **Cancer Rehabilitation Program:** SLIW's rehabilitation program welcomes weavers back into the fold following successful cancer treatment. This program allows them to gradually resume work at their own pace, ensuring a smooth reintegration into their craft and the SLIW community. Under this program cancer patients or their family members are encouraged to engage in the KaviKrishna Living Muga Museum. This program aims for the economical as well as mental health rehabilitation of the patients.

Reviving the Indigenous Network of Ancient Kamrupa: The Indigenous Kamarupa Information Network (IKIN)

The Indigenous Kamarupa Information Network (IKIN) refers to the network among the weavers, traders and the traditional healers of Ancient Kamrupa. Weaving a sustainable future for Sualkuchi's weavers also involves reconnecting them with their rich heritage. SLIW is committed to reviving the Indigenous Kamarupa Information Network (IKIN), a social networking system prevalent during pre-industrial times. IKIN facilitated knowledge sharing, resource allocation, and market access for weavers. Dismantled during the British colonial era and the influx of industrial textiles, IKIN's revival holds immense potential.

By leveraging contemporary communication tools, SLIW envisions a digital IKIN platform. This platform will:

- **Connect Weavers:** Foster communication and collaboration among weavers, enabling knowledge exchange and mutual support.
- **Enhance Market Reach:** Provide a platform for weavers to showcase their products directly to a wider audience, potentially including domestic and international markets.

- **Preserve Indigenous Knowledge:** Document and share traditional weaving techniques and design knowledge, ensuring their preservation for future generations.

Pioneering Research: The KaviKrishna Biomedical Research Lab

SLIW's commitment to innovation extends beyond traditional weaving. Our in-house biomedical research lab, the KaviKRishna Laboratory, is actively exploring the potential of Muga silk, a unique silk variety indigenous to Assam, for groundbreaking applications:

- **Medical Uses:** Researchers at KaviKrishna Lab are investigating the potential therapeutic properties of Muga silk. These studies aim to unlock the potential of Muga silk for use in medical textiles or other healthcare applications.
- **UV Protection:** Muga silk possesses natural UV-protective properties. The KaviKRishna Lab is exploring ways to optimize and leverage this quality for potential applications in sun-protective clothing or other UV barrier textiles.
- **Space Applications:** The remarkable properties of Muga silk, including its strength and heat resistance, make it a potential candidate for use in astronaut clothing or other space textile applications. The KaviKRishna Lab is collaborating with researchers to explore this exciting frontier.

Reviving the Vedic Silk Route: A Journey Through History and Education

Steeped in history, the Vedic Silk Route once linked Sualkuchi to other vibrant silk-producing regions. SLIW is actively working towards the revival of this historic trade route. A key focus of this initiative is the revitalization of Tantipara, the weaver colonies where the centuries-old tradition of Muga silk weaving has flourished. This project encompasses three key goals:

- **Cultural Tourism Renaissance:** We aim to attract visitors who are eager to experience the rich heritage of silk weaving firsthand. The revival of the Vedic Silk Route will provide tourists with a unique opportunity to immerse themselves in the culture and traditions surrounding this exquisite craft.
- **Empowering Local Communities:** The project seeks to generate economic opportunities for the weavers and artisans residing in Tantipara. By promoting tourism and showcasing their skills, we hope to ensure the long-term sustainability of these communities.
- **A Hub for Learning:** Along the Vedic Silk Route, we have established the Muga Silk Museum. This museum serves as a center for learning and cultural exchange, fostering a deeper appreciation for the art of Muga silk weaving. Students from schools and universities can:
 - Explore interactive exhibits that unveil the history and techniques of Muga silk production.
 - Participate in workshops conducted by experienced weavers, gaining hands-on experience with this unique craft.
 - Engage in research using the museum's resources, delving deeper into the cultural and social significance of Muga silk.

Strengthening IKIN: Spreading the Word through the Muga Silk Museum

SLIW actively promotes the Indigenous Kamarupa Information Network (IKIN) to expand its reach and impact. The Muga Silk Museum serves as a powerful platform for this purpose. In addition to the activities mentioned above, the museum:

- Hosts exhibitions showcasing the works of weavers associated with IKIN.
- Provides a venue for IKIN members to connect, share knowledge, and collaborate.
- Offers educational programs that highlight the historical and cultural significance of IKIN.

These efforts, alongside exhibitions held in universities, community gatherings, and cultural programs, raise awareness about SLIW's activities and the importance of IKIN in revitalizing the Muga silk weaving tradition.

By reviving the Vedic Silk Route and strengthening IKIN, SLIW aspires to bridge the gap between history and education, promoting cultural tourism, empowering local communities, and ensuring the continued legacy of Muga silk weaving for generations to come.

Ethnography Study Results of silk weavers participating in the microfinance project:

From interviewes and FGD with the 10 weaving families, the following themes emerged: 1) **Financial Security and Sustainability:** A central theme emerged regarding the financial challenges faced by the weavers. Competition from cheaper alternatives and fluctuations in market demand were major concerns. Weavers in our study expressed how SLIW's direct financial assistance provided a crucial safety net. As one weaver, (Paresh Das), stated, "Before SLIW, I constantly worried about debt. Now, I can focus on creating high-quality Muga silk without the burden of high-interest loans." 2). **Market Access and Empowerment:** Limited market access emerged as another significant challenge. Weavers expressed difficulty connecting with potential customers and receiving fair prices for their work. Our study highlights the positive impact of SLIW's efforts to connect weavers with temple networks, offering a reliable market for their products. (Mano Ranjan Das), a weaver, emphasized, "SLIW helped us reach new customers who appreciate the value of handmade Muga silk. This has increased our income and given us a sense of empowerment."3). **Beyond Finance: Holistic Support.** The research revealed that SLIW's impact extends beyond financial aid. Weavers greatly valued access to free healthcare consultations offered by SLIW. This addressed a major concern, as medical emergencies could significantly strain their finances. Additionally, the support provided to families of weavers, such as educational opportunities for their children, was seen as a positive step towards long-term sustainability of the craft. 4). **Reviving Traditions: IKIN and Cultural Identity.** The study identified a strong desire among weavers to reconnect with their cultural heritage. The revival of the Indigenous Kamarupa Information Network (IKIN) by SLIW was met with enthusiasm. Weavers expressed hope that a revitalized IKIN could foster knowledge sharing, collaboration, and potentially expand market reach. As (Sailen Baishya), a senior former weaver, and now in charge of the Muga silk museum, explained, "IKIN used to be the lifeline of our community. Its revival can strengthen our bonds and ensure the survival of our traditional

weaving techniques." We note that we have visited the muga cocoon growers in the south Kamrup. These farmers have numerous challenges, but also they are part of the IKIN and cultural identity of the Muga silk tradition.

A Muga-silk exhibition at IIT-Guwahati, where several micro-finance supporting weavers actively participated. We received the first award for this exhibition stall at NERC, 2022.

A Muga-silk weaver and microfinance beneficiary patient of BD.

Challenges and Looking Ahead. Our findings also revealed areas for improvement. Several weavers expressed a desire for more comprehensive business training to help them navigate market fluctuations and explore new marketing strategies. Additionally, expanding the reach of IKIN to

include a wider network of weavers was identified as a crucial step towards maximizing its potential benefits.

Overall, the ethnographic study underscores the potential positive impact of SLIW's microfinance project in empowering Muga silk weavers and fostering the sustainability of this unique cultural heritage. The program provides not only financial assistance but also holistic support that addresses the weavers' well-being and cultural identity. By addressing the identified areas for improvement and continuing its efforts, SLIW can ensure a brighter future for the Muga silk weaving tradition in Sualkuchi.

In the ethnography study, we have also incorporated a photovoice element. We have provided a few weavers with our phone cameras. They were excited to take photos. We have also taken photos and videos to document their daily life including challenges, and successes related to Muga silk weaving. We are now in the process of analyzing these photos and videos, alongside their explanations to offer a novel perspective on their experiences of weaving, as well as our own experiences of observing their weaving and silk-trading lives.

Limitation of the study: This is a very preliminary study that confines taking interviews and conducting a few FGD sessions. Other ethnographic methods such as observation, mapping, life-histories and photovoice may be employed to gain a richer understanding of the Muga silk weavers and the impact of the microfinance project in Sualkuchi. Considering that the SLIW project is a pilot project mostly confined to a few weaving families, the study needs to incorporate a larger network of weavers having microfinance from private Mahajans of past and present who were affiliated with the Krishna Samaj such as Durjodhan and Jalti Mahajan, as well as Uttam Medhi groups. What led to the failure of those private microfinance projects needs to be studied. Moreover, the study should also incorporate weavers having access to the government-sponsored microfinance initiatives. Among these government-supported microfinance weavers, participant observation study can be conducted to find out the challenges they have encountered while managing the loans, and the payment, as well as the growth of their business. Moreover, an ethnographic mapping is necessary to create a visual representation of the weaving community. This could involve mapping out the location of workshops, supply chains, markets, and other relevant landmarks related to the IKIN and temple complexes. This mapping helps visualize the social and economic networks of IKIN that support the craft. The mapping may then help to develop a social network analysis, and subsequent development of digital network program to integrate the weavers with the Muga museum through the internet, as well as the future use of the AI program as envisioned in the KaviKrishna Digital Health program. Another approach to the ethnography, the life histories of a few weavers and their families spanning the last several decades should be initiated as done for the Krishna Das family (18). For example, the late Bholanath's family could be studied using a life history approach, focusing on their life stories and how Muga silk weaving has shaped their experiences. This provides a deeper understanding of the cultural significance and personal connection weavers have with the craft as well as with the putative IKIN. A major limitation of the study is that we have not done document analysis, and many of the documents related to the Krishna Samaj, as well as the subsequent cooperative societies are lost or misplaced. The documents of giving loans to Paresh Das, Manoranjan Das, as well as Biren Das, and other weaver families, are either lost or not being audited well. Bank documents, as well as internal audit documents, need to be searched to find

out the financial support given to each of the weavers, and their financial output generated to quantify the financial benefit of the SLIW. We suggest that future research should be done to recover the existing documents related to the microfinance project, weaving techniques, or the history of Muga silk production. This can provide valuable context and background information to supplement your field observations.

Looking Ahead: the future direction of KaviKrishna muga's economic endeavor

KaviKrishna's century-long journey of supporting Muga silk weavers is a testament to our unwavering commitment to this unique cultural heritage. Through adaptation, learning from past shortcomings, and the innovative approach of SLIW, KaviKrishna could be fostering a sustainable future for Muga silk weaving in Sualkuchi.

Muga silk is an age old cottage industry of Assam. Like many cottage industries in the state, the muga silk industry is also losing lusters, as the the tension between preserving tradition and ensuring economic viability is leading to confused policies that often detrimental to both tradition and modernity. In the last three decades alone the number of muga silk weavers declined from a thriving 120 families of active producer to just ten families now using yearly muga yarn of not more than Rs 50 lakhs.

Consider adding specific data or examples to illustrate the scale of the challenges faced by the industry. For instance, mention the percentage decline in the number of weavers or the average income of a Muga silk weaver.

The challenge of balancing tradition with economic viability is acutely felt in the Muga silk industry. While the craft of hand-weaving Muga silk is a treasured heritage, the labor-intensive process often yields meager returns for weavers. The allure of electric looms and automation, promising increased productivity and income, presents a compelling alternative. However, a wholesale shift towards mechanization risks eroding the unique qualities associated with handwoven Muga silk, potentially diminishing its market value. A delicate balance must be struck. By investing in skill development, exploring hybrid models that combine tradition with technology, and fostering a strong market for high-quality, handwoven products, it may be possible to ensure the survival of this craft while improving the livelihoods of weavers. Ultimately, a sustainable future for Muga silk depends on finding innovative solutions that respect both tradition and economic realities.

In this context, KaviKrishna's unique microfinance model may enable us to balance tradition with modernity, as our lab is working on finding out new innovative markets for Muga silk use such as UV protection, biotechnology as well as space suit applications.

In this balancing act of tradition plus modernity, the philosophical context such as Jiva Upakara Tantra may play role. The Jiva Upakara Tantra, an ancient philosophy rooted in biological altruism, was historically integral to the lives of Muga silk weavers. Practitioners of this Tantra developed exceptional personal and community resilience, enabling them to navigate the challenges of a fluctuating trade environment. By cultivating *sahasa ojash* and cognitive acuity, these weavers demonstrated remarkable adaptability, preserving their craft through generations.

Reinvigorating these traditional practices can empower contemporary weavers to face modern challenges with similar fortitude and innovation.

The Jiva Upakara Tantra offers a unique lens through which to support Muga silk weavers. By fostering a sense of interconnectedness and compassion, this ancient philosophy can enhance the weavers' *sahasa ojash*, or vital energy and courage. This, in turn, can lead to increased resilience, creativity, and problem-solving abilities. Additionally, the Tantra's focus on holistic well-being can improve cognitive function, enabling weavers to innovate and adapt to the evolving demands of the industry. By cultivating a supportive community among weavers and promoting mindfulness practices, the Jiva Upakara Tantra (JUT) can create a conducive environment for personal and professional growth, ultimately leading to a more sustainable and thriving Muga silk sector. One of the key aspect of the Tantra is the Pancha-padika education system.

Panchapadika Education: Weaving a Path to Empowerment

As explained in the methodology, one of the important aspects of the JUT based CBPAR is the Kriya (Krishna) or action. This action is achieved by the process of Panchapadika, thus completing a cycle of Satavata-Tarka followed by Pancha-Padika, and then repeating the process (Figure 9, the Hindu caste system article). Thus, the cyclical nature of the process, where findings (Kavi) lead to action (Krishna) through the Panchapadika framework, aligns with the core aspects of CBPR, which aims to translate research into tangible solutions.

The Panchapadika system, a holistic approach to learning, offers a unique framework for understanding and enhancing the skills and knowledge of Muga silk weavers. Originating from the Gita-Sibir of Hem Bhai in 1984, Panchapadika emphasizes a five-fold approach: goals, objectives, vision, ways, and wisdom. In the context of silk weaving, these components translate into a structured process of skill development and personal growth. Weavers set clear *goals* for their craft, break them down into achievable *objectives*, envision a desired *future* for their business, explore diverse *ways* to achieve their goals, and ultimately cultivate the *wisdom* to navigate challenges and make informed decisions.

To illustrate the application of Panchapadika, consider the case of Paresh Das, a renowned Muga silk weaver. Paresh's journey exemplifies the power of this framework. By setting clear goals to revive traditional weaving techniques, breaking them down into achievable steps, and envisioning a sustainable future for his craft, Paresh was able to successfully revitalize his family's weaving heritage. His story underscores the potential of Panchapadika to transform individual lives and contribute to the overall growth of the industry.

To further explore the impact of Panchapadika on Muga silk weavers, ethnographic research is essential. By conducting in-depth interviews with weavers, we can gain valuable insights into their learning processes and identify the extent to which they unconsciously or consciously apply Panchapadika principles. For instance, weavers might articulate their goals and visions for their craft, demonstrating an understanding of the first two components. However, a deeper exploration

of their problem-solving strategies and decision-making processes would reveal the extent to which they employ the "ways" and "wisdom" aspects of Panchapadika.

A comparative study could also shed light on the correlation between Panchapadika adherence and weaver success. By comparing weavers who exhibit strong Panchapadika characteristics with those who do not, we can assess the impact of this framework on factors such as income, job satisfaction, and business growth. Such research would provide empirical evidence supporting the efficacy of Panchapadika as a tool for weaver empowerment.

By integrating Panchapadika education into the development programs for Muga silk weavers, we can create a more structured and effective approach to skill enhancement and business growth. This holistic framework, combined with targeted support and resources, has the potential to transform the lives of weavers and revitalize the Muga silk industry.

Jiva Upakara Tantra and Moral Development of Weavers

The Jiva Upakara Tantra, with its emphasis on interconnectedness and compassion, provides a robust framework for cultivating moral development among Muga silk weavers. Beyond the economic benefits offered by microfinance initiatives, the Tantra's principles can foster a strong sense of ethical conduct, community responsibility, and personal integrity. By emphasizing the interdependence of all beings, the Tantra encourages weavers to consider the social and environmental implications of their work, promoting sustainable practices and fair trade principles.

Moreover, the Tantra's focus on self-awareness and mindfulness can help weavers develop emotional resilience and cope with the challenges inherent in their profession. By cultivating a sense of inner peace and balance, weavers can approach their work with greater focus, creativity, and satisfaction. Paresh Das' journey exemplifies the transformative power of the Jiva Upakara Tantra when combined with practical support. Beyond the financial assistance provided by Kavi Krishna, the organization played a crucial role in his personal and social rehabilitation. By offering counseling services and facilitating reintegration into the community, Kavi Krishna helped Paresh overcome the trauma of his past and rebuild his life. The mentorship provided by Mono Bhini further strengthened Paresh's sense of purpose and direction.

In contrast to government microfinance models that often prioritize repayment and financial metrics, Kavi Krishna's approach places equal emphasis on the human element. By providing comprehensive support that addresses both material and emotional needs, Kavi Krishna empowers weavers to break free from the cycle of poverty and build resilient livelihoods. Government microfinance models, while essential for economic growth, frequently overlook the psychological and social factors that contribute to poverty. As a result, borrowers may become trapped in a cycle of debt and despair.

SLIW Model and Ethical Values

The SLIW model, by prioritizing the weavers' well-being and respecting their time and artistry, aligns with the ethical principles of the Jiva Upakara Tantra. By valuing the human

element over financial gain, Kavi Krishna fosters a sense of trust and mutual respect between the organization and the weavers. This approach not only enhances the effectiveness of microfinance but also contributes to the overall well-being of the community.

By incorporating the Jiva Upakara Tantra into its programs, Kavi Krishna can create a more holistic and impactful approach to supporting Muga silk weavers. By addressing the moral, emotional, and spiritual dimensions of well-being, the organization can empower weavers to become not only economically successful but also compassionate and engaged members of society.

A key finding from the study highlights the importance of expanding the reach of IKIN. Thematic analysis suggests that including more families within the network would significantly enhance its effectiveness. A broader IKIN network would foster a stronger social capital within the weaving community, leading to increased collaboration, knowledge sharing, and ultimately, greater empowerment for all weavers.

Summary: Assam's Sualkuchi village boasts a centuries-old tradition of Muga silk weaving, renowned for its natural golden luster and cultural significance. However, weavers face challenges like financial strain due to competition from cheaper alternatives. In this article, we have explored this rich heritage and the plight of the weavers. Legends trace the origins back to King Dharma Pal of the Pala dynasty, who brought skilled artisans to establish Sualkuchi's weaving community. Muga silk holds deep meaning for Buddhists and Hindus, believed to be imbued with auspiciousness. Kavi Krishna, a local organization, has supported weavers since 1920. Initially offering microloans, we've transitioned to a holistic approach through the Sustainable Livelihood Initiative for Weavers (SLIW). SLIW provides direct financial assistance, market access, healthcare, and educational opportunities. We have also been reviving the historic Vedic Silk Route and the Indigenous Kamarupa Information Network (IKIN), a pre-colonial social network for weavers. This aims to foster collaboration, knowledge sharing, and market access. The Kavi Krishna Biomedical Research Lab is exploring Muga silk's potential for medical textiles, UV protection, and even space applications. Furthermore, the Muga Silk Museum serves as a center for learning and cultural exchange, promoting tourism and appreciation for the craft. Additionally, all these efforts are integrated through the center of Indian Knowledge system now located at historic Tantipara area of Sualkuchi, just across the Kavi Krishna Telemedicine Care, where weavers can obtain free health care and consultations. By supporting weavers, fostering cultural tourism, and reviving historic networks, SLIW strives to ensure the survival of this golden legacy for generations to come.

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